

Effect of Different Tunnelling Method In Silty Soil on Settlement of Raft Foundations

Shashikant Chaubey¹, Anurag Misra² and Sivakumar G³

^{1,2&3}Indian Institute of Technology Jammu, India

Abstract This research article provides a thorough investigation of the settling behavior of raft foundations under the effect of several tunnelling technologies, namely the New Austrian Tunnelling approach (NATM) and the Tunnel Boring Machine (TBM) approach. The correlation between ground movements caused by tunnelling and nearby structures, namely raft foundations, is a crucial element in urban development, particularly in areas with extensive subterranean infrastructure developments. The study utilizes sophisticated numerical modelling using PLAXIS 3D methodologies to replicate the intricate dynamics between tunnel excavation and the underlying soil-structure system. The study aims to examine the impact of several parameters, including excavation depth, lateral distance between raft and tunnel centerline, on the settlement response of raft foundations. This will be achieved through a series of parametric studies. The primary objective of the comparative evaluation is to evaluate and analyze the respective advantages and disadvantages of different tunnelling methods in relation to their potential effects on nearby foundations. In addition, the inclusion of field data from carefully chosen case studies serves to authenticate the numerical findings, so guaranteeing the significance and practicality of the outcomes in real-life situations. This study examines the consequences of settlement variations on the structural integrity of raft foundations.

Keywords Foundations, Raft, Tunneling

Introduction

The exponential urban expansion, accompanied by increased congestion and significant traffic issues, leads growing demand for infrastructure has led to a heightened focus on shallow, soft ground tunnelling techniques in urban areas that are densely populated with various surface and subsurface structures. In such contexts, underground construction activities become particularly sensitive to the effects of ground deformation, which must be carefully managed and restricted to an acceptable level. Surface settlement resulting from tunnelling arises when the process of excavating tunnels modifies the tension and displacement of the adjacent soil, causing movements of the earth at the surface. The degree of settlement is influenced by factors such as tunnel depth, soil type, and building methods. Excessive settling of the ground might pose threats to existing structures. To address this issue, mitigating methods such as pre-support systems and compensatory grouting are necessary. Studied of 3D building performance due to excavation of tunnel and predicts the risk of building damage induced by 3D ground displacements due to tunnelling[1]. Developed a 3D numerical model for tunneling and evaluates the tunnel lining behavior and ground displacement[2]. investigates the stability of a shallow circular tunnel in cohesionless soil with support conditions like those found during construction [3]. As tunnel depth increases, the effect boundary of the excavation narrows, and under varying tunnel volume losses, the impact range of the excavation remains consistent [4]. Analyze construction or service risk, transverse trough edge lateral motions can be as important as vertical settlement [5]. Improving supporting parameters and employing extra support systems can aid in the prevention of damage to tunnel structures and aboveground structures [6]. The article acknowledges that empirical and analytical methods fail to account for enough effective parameters on settlement, whereas numerical methods, such as FEM and FDM, have been widely applied and demonstrate adequate performance when analyzing tunnel excavation-induced surface settlement [7]. By comparing the results of centrifuge experiments to the proposed method and performing parametric analyses to determine how the relative location of the raft and sediment influences the relationship between deflection ratio and bending strain, the study verifies the method [8]. Pure soil is less resistant to deformation than stiffer structures [9]. The observed subsurface settlement data corresponds well with the predicted curves based on the normal probability model, indicating that the approach is applicable [10]. Analytical methods for predicting surface settlement due to tunnelling employ mathematical equations to provide precise insights of surface settlement. Analytical solution compared with actual measurements and found good agreement with actual data [11]. The derived empirical formula and analytical solution work well in surface settlement prediction [12]. presents semi-analytical solutions for predicting ground movements in shallow tunnels. [4] Peck-Gaussian function-based empirical techniques offer adequate modelling for trough breadth and settlement. Raft foundations are essential for sustaining structures on different types of soil in metropolitan environments. Their extensive application results from their capacity to disperse loads uniformly, offering stability in a range of complex and sometimes demanding subsurface circumstances. [14] New raft foundation design criteria are recommended and numerical analyses the HS model to simulate soil behavior. [15] Study on tunneling effects on soft clay and sandy soil and analysis of TBM tunnel construction and soil behavior.[16] Comparative analysis of 2D and 3D finite element models for the simulation of tunnelling in granular soil beneath an existing raft foundation.[8] Enhancing the stiffness of the raft reduces both settling and tensile stresses.[17] Piled raft foundations are an economical design for deep foundations. [18] Study about the size and load effect of raft.[19] A failure criterion is proposed for the tunnel face in the general case of a cohesive and frictional soil, and charts are provided to allow a bracketed estimate of the required retaining pressure. [20] The influence effect of the shield tunneling method on the surface buildings during

tunnel construction is studied, which can provide a relevant basis for the planning of subway tunnel lines. [21] Tunnel Boring Machines (TBM) with Earth Pressure Balance (EPB) technology are utilized for excavating tunnels in metropolitan environments. They are also employed to study the impact of construction factors on ground displacements.[22] In tunnelling operations, it is crucial to manage and forecast the ground surface settlements that occur during and after the excavation process. These settlements have the potential to harm the structures located on the earth's surface. [23] investigates the interaction between tunnelling activities in soft soils and nearby structures. [24] investigates the impact of TBM tunnelling on an existing raft foundation that is supported by granular soils. For making predictions about the settling of a raft caused by tunnelling in numerical modelling, it is crucial to use a suitable soil model. It is important to appropriately depict factors like soil stiffness, consolidation properties, and the interaction between the soil and tunnelling process. [25] HS model accurately captures stress-strain/volumetric-strain responses.[26] This research analyses experimental data from oedometer and triaxial testing on Bangkok subsoils to estimate stiffness and strength characteristics for the Hardening Soil Model. Geological conditions, TBM type, tunnel alignment, upkeep, groundwater, tunnel diameter, cutterhead design, face support, and environmental factors all have an impact on TBM tunnelling. [27] Surface settlement decreases with increasing face pressure and grout pressure. [28] The volume loss will not occur if the grout pressure and the bentonite pressure are larger than the vertical soil pressure and [29] the volume loss will not occur if the grout pressure and the bentonite pressure are larger than the vertical soil pressure, [30] The influence of mechanical properties of grout material of tail void grouting on ground deformation. [31] Evaluate the critical supporting face pressure and grout pressure by observation of the vertical deformation and horizontal displacement of soil body during tunneling [32] The material properties play significant role in distribution of loads in the surrounding materials [33] width of the subsurface settlement trough decreases with increasing depth, and the subsurface maximum settlement increases with increasing depth. [34] Evaluated the influence of the face and grouting pressure and the TBM design. Surface settlement decreases with increasing face pressure and grout pressure.[35] The volume loss will not occur if the grout pressure and the bentonite pressure are larger than the vertical soil pressure. [36] An Increase in the face pressure and backfill pressure doesn't always lead to a decrease in surface settlement, but there are the critical face and back fill pressure combination. Considerable research has been undertaken to investigate the effects of tunnelling activities on foundation settlements. However, there is a significant knowledge gap regarding the specific influence of the New Austrian Tunnelling Method (NATM) and the Tunnel Boring Machine (TBM) method on raft foundations in urban settings. The existing body of literature predominantly centers on the general settlements caused by tunnels, frequently neglecting the intricate interconnections that emerge from the distinctive attributes of these two extensively utilized tunnelling approaches. The prevailing body of research commonly generalizes the impacts of tunnelling, without thoroughly examining the specific comparative analysis necessary to distinguish the distinct consequences of New Austrian Tunnelling Method (NATM) and Tunnel Boring Machine (TBM) on raft foundations. Acknowledging the prevalence of these sorts of foundations in urban development, it is imperative to address this knowledge gap to enhance the accuracy and efficacy of engineering practices.

Validation of Numerical model

Before going to the actual modelling first, the validation of result is carried out by existing literature, empirical method, analytical method centrifuge modelling or case studies. In this thesis for the TBM approach the surface settlement is validated for the 12.5m overburden using numerical method [37], whose hardening soil parameters are given in table 1. The face slurry pressure is simulated as an axial pressure of 200 kPa that increases linearly with depth by 15 kPa/m and radial pressure of 140 kPa that increases linearly with depth by 15 kPa/m and boundary condition is shown by fig 1. The tunnel advancement process is simulated by dividing the tunnel into 1.5m segments and total length for tunnelling process is 45m. The raft possesses certain properties, including dimensions of 20 m × 20 m, a thickness of 1.0 m, and the application of loads in a manner that results in an average stress of 100 kPa underneath the raft. Fig 2 and Fig 3 show a good agreement with result obtained by Plaxis 3D model and Elmouchi et al.

Fig. 1. Raft configuration and model boundaries.

Table 1. Suggested characteristics of granular soils with varying relative densities

Soil type (Hardening Soil)	Medium Dense soil
Saturated unit weight, γ_{sat} (kN/m ³)	18
Secant stiffness in standard drained triaxial test, E_{50}^{ref} (MPa)	35
Tangent stiffness for primary oedometer loading, E_{oed}^{ref} (MPa)	35
Unloading/reloading stiffness, E_{ur}^{ref} (MPa)	105
Power for stress-level dependency of Stiffness, m .	0.5
Effective cohesion, c' (kPa).	0.01
Effective angle of shearing resistance, ϕ (°)	35
Poisson's ratio, ν_{ur}	0.25
Earth pressure coefficient at rest, K_o	0.47

Fig. 2. Maximum settlement of raft foundation during tunnel advancement

Fig. 3. The effect of tunnel diameter (D) on raft settling

Methodology

The raft possesses certain properties, including dimensions of 20 m × 20 m, a thickness of 1.0 m, and the application of loads in a manner that results in an average stress of 100 kPa underneath the raft, and raft is stimulated as a plate element

and its properties are Young's modulus $E = 2 \times 10^7 \text{ kN/m}^2$, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.15$ and situated at a depth of 1m. Figure 4 displays the depicted raft structure and model boundaries. The tunnel diameter (D) is 6.5 m. The length of the tunnel boring machine (TBM) body is 9 meters. Additionally, the plate of the TBM in the 9 m segment is activated with jacking forces in the first plane, while the tunnel pressure is applied in the last plane of the TBM. In the process of tunnel excavation, each step indicates 3 meters. The tunnel lining is composed of concrete rings which are simulated as a linear elastic concrete material with weight (w) of 24 kN/m^2 , and Poisson's ratio (ν) of 0.15, thickness is 0.5m. The model considers the many phases involved in the building of tunnels. Soil properties are shown in table 2, and the soil would be categorized as CL (Low Cohesion, High Friction Angle) according to the Indian Standard soil classification system.

Fig. 4. The suggested raft arrangement and model boundaries.

Table 2. Geotechnical Properties of Silty Soil

Soil type (Hardening Soil)	Silty soil (ML)
Saturated unit weight, γ_{sat} (kN/m^3)	20
Secant stiffness in standard drained triaxial test, E_{50}^{ref} (MPa)	61
Tangent stiffness for primary oedometer loading, E_{oed}^{ref} (MPa)	61
Unloading/reloading stiffness, E_{ur}^{ref} (MPa)	192
Power for stress-level dependency of Stiffness, m	0.85
Effective cohesion, c' (kPa).	20
Effective angle of shearing resistance, ϕ ($^\circ$)	32
Poisson's ratio, ν_{ur}	0.3
Earth pressure coefficient at rest, K_0	0.61

Result and Comparison

Fig. 5 clearly represents a notable correlation between tunnelling parameters and settlement results. As the depth of tunnel excavation rises, the corresponding settlement generally decreases. Concurrently, when the distance between the tunnel centerline and the raft foundation increases from centerline of raft foundation to 20m away from centerline, a corresponding decrease in settlement is noticed. The New Austrian Tunnelling Method (NATM) is a highly versatile and adaptable tunnelling technology renowned for its efficacy in many soil compositions, particularly silty soils. The implementation of the New Austrian Tunnelling Method (NATM) on soil with a high silt content involves the combination of excavation and immediate support measures. Tunnelling encounters distinct difficulties when dealing with silty soils, which are identifiable by their small particles because of their high vulnerability to ground displacement. NATM tackles

Fig. 5. Raft foundation settlement profiles during tunnel advancement by TBM tunnelling method. (a) 10m depth (b) 15m depth (c) 20m depth and (d) 25m depth.

these difficulties by utilizing a methodical approach. At first, the front of the tunnel is dug out, and the soil that is uncovered is upheld using a mixture of shotcrete and other methods of reinforcement. This prompt assistance helps to stabilize the tunnel face and avert earth collapse. [38] A three-dimensional model is preferable for statistical study of the random field of NATM tunnels since it offers a more thorough assessment of surface settlement conditions in comparison to two-dimensional approaches. [39] The utilization of three-dimensional finite element software enables the creation of numerical models to examine the stability and efficiency of the tunnel at various stages of construction. This analysis considers the reinforced soil slope, which is subjected to the loads imposed by buildings and vehicles. [40] stress distributions in various excavation sequences were examined, yielding additional insights into the tunnel’s behavior throughout the construction process. In the numerical modelling of NATM tunnel construction, the excavation process is initiated using the heading and benching method. Simultaneously, the outer surface is activated as shotcrete with specific material properties, including a thickness of 30 cm, unit weight of 25 kN/m³, and Young’s modulus of 26×10^6 kN/m². Additionally, steel ribs, modelled as beam elements, are introduced at 1.5 m intervals with material properties such as a Young’s modulus of 20×10^7 kN/m², cross-sectional area of 4710 mm², moment of inertia of 220,000 mm⁴, and a unit weight of 3200 kN/m³. Fig.6 shows that during the modelling analysis, it was determined that raft settlement decreases as tunnel depth increases. Deeper tunnel excavations disperse ground movements across a greater volume, thereby diminishing the impact on the raft foundation. This result is consistent with initial expectations. Nevertheless, an intriguing subtlety surfaced when evaluating the impact of the lateral distance separating the centerline of the raft and the tunnel. An increase in lateral distance was related to a marginal rise in raft settlement, which contradicted the expected pattern. This observation highlights the significance of incorporating lateral distances as a crucial element when optimizing tunnelling parameters to reduce raft settlements, even when lining properties remain constant.

Fig. 6. Raft foundation settlement profiles during tunnel advancement by NATM tunnelling method. (a) 10m depth (b) 15m depth (c) 20m depth and (d) 25m depth.

Conclusion

The present study investigates the impact of different tunnelling methods on the settlement of raft foundations in c-φ (Silty) soil. The numerical analysis was performed by considering the varying depth of tunnel position and lateral distance between raft foundation and tunnel centerline. The following are the key findings:

- Settlements of raft foundations were found to be less significant when the New Austrian Tunneling Method (NATM) is utilized compared to the Tunnel Boring Machine (TBM) approach.
- The variation in settlement outcomes between NATM and TBM can be attributed to the inherent adaptability and flexibility of the NATM. This method's capacity to provide immediate support via steel ribs and shotcrete application allows for a more controlled excavation process, reducing ground movements and consequent settlements in the adjacent soil.
- Raft foundation settlement decreases as the tunnel's depth increases and the distance between the foundation and the tunnel's centerline increases.
- Settlement of the raft foundation increases as the tunnel face approaches within 1.5 D, (where D is diameter of tunnel) of influence from the raft edge, with settlement rising progressively as one moves towards the raft's centerline. The effect of the tunnel on the raft is noticeable up to a lateral distance of 3D between the raft's centerline and the tunnel's centerline.
- Beyond the 3D lateral distance, the settlement of the raft foundation diminishes significantly, indicating that the impact of the tunnel on the raft becomes negligible at greater distances from the tunnel's centerline.

References

1. Namazi, E., Mohamad, H., & Hajihassani, M. (2021), "3D behaviour of buildings due to tunnel induced ground movement", *Transportation Geotechnics*, 31:100661.
2. Do, N. A., Dias, D., Oreste, P., & Djeran-Maigre, I. (2014), "Three-dimensional numerical simulation for mechanized tunnelling in soft ground: the influence of the joint pattern", *Acta Geotechnica*, 9:673-694.
3. J. H. Atkinson and D. M. Po, (1977), "Stability of A Shallow Circular Tunnel in Cohesionless".
4. T. Wang, R. Wang, F. Xue, And N. Tang, (2023), "Experimental Investigation on The Effect of Volume Loss on Ground Movements Induced By Tunnelling In Sand," *KSCE Journal Of Civil Engineering*, 27:122–134.
5. Rankin, W. J. (1988), "Ground movements resulting from urban tunnelling: predictions and effects", *Geological Society, London, Engineering Geology Special Publications*, 5:79-92.
6. Kun, M. (2015), "The effect of shallow depth tunnelling on aboveground constructions", *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 8:5247-5256.

7. Moeinossadat, S. R., & Ahangari, K. (2019), "Estimating maximum surface settlement due to EPBM tunneling by Numerical-Intelligent approach—A case study: Tehran subway line", *Transportation Geotechnics*, 18:92-102.
8. Yu, J., Leung, C. F., Huang, M., & Fu, Y. (2021), "Centrifuge and theoretical study on tunnel-raft interaction in clay", *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 115:104038.
9. Cao, L., Zhang, D., Fang, Q., & Yu, L. (2020), "Movements of ground and existing structures induced by slurry pressure-balance tunnel boring machine (SPB TBM) tunnelling in clay", *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 97:103278.
10. Fang, Y. S., Wu, C. T., Chen, S. F., & Liu, C. (2014), "An estimation of subsurface settlement due to shield tunneling", *Tunnelling and underground space technology*, 44:121-129.
11. Chou, W. I., & Bobet, A. (2002), "Predictions of ground deformations in shallow tunnels in clay", *Tunnelling and underground space technology*, 17:3-19.
12. Wang, F., Du, X., & Li, P. (2023), "Predictions of ground surface settlement for shield tunnels in sandy cobble stratum based on stochastic medium theory and empirical formulas", *Underground Space*, 11:189-203.
13. Yu, L., Zhang, D., Fang, Q., Xu, T., Luo, J., & Chen, W. (2023), "Semi-analytical solutions of three-dimensional ground movements due to shallow tunnelling", *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 136:105074.
14. Zakhem, A. M., & El Naggar, H. (2020), "Three-dimensional investigation of how newly constructed buildings supported on raft foundations affect pre-existing tunnels", *Transportation Geotechnics*, 22: 100324.
15. Zakaria, W. A., & Abbas, H. O. (2022), "Numerical analysis of tunneling influences progress on soft clay bearing a raft foundation", *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions*, 7:303.
16. Siddiqua, S., ElMouchi, A., Hassan, A. M., & Amer, M. I. (2018), "Comparison of 2D and 3D finite element models of tunnelling in granular soil under existing raft foundation", In 71st Canadian Geotechnical Conference.
17. Sinha, A., & Hanna, A. M. (2017), "3D numerical model for piled raft foundation", *International Journal of Geomechanics*, 17:04016055.
18. Le Ba, V., Van, N. N., & Le Ba, K. (2018), "Study on the settlement of raft foundations by different methods", In MATEC Web of conferences, 251: 04054.
19. Leca, E., & Dormieux, L. (1990), "Upper and lower bound solutions for the face stability of shallow circular tunnels in frictional material", *Géotechnique*, 40:581-606.
20. Wang, C. (2019), "Influence of underground geotechnical operation on surface buildings through the shield method", *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 12:649.
21. Lambrughi, A., Rodríguez, L. M., & Castellanza, R. (2012), "Development and validation of a 3D numerical model for TBM-EPB mechanised excavations", *Computers and Geotechnics*, 40: 97-113.
22. Abdullah, R. A. (2016), "A review on selection of tunneling method and parameters effecting ground settlements", *Electronic Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, 21:4459-75.
23. Mroueh, H., & Shahrour, I. (2003), "A full 3-D finite element analysis of tunneling-adjacent structures interaction", *Computers and Geotechnics*, 30:245-253.
24. ElMouchi, A. M., Hassan, A. M., & Amer, M. I. (2018), "Performance of an existing raft foundation rested on granular soils due to TBM tunneling process", *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 11:1-11.
25. Sukkarak, R., Likitlersuang, S., Jongpradist, P., & Jamsawang, P. (2021), "Strength and stiffness parameters for hardening soil model of rockfill materials", *Soils and Foundations*, 61:1597-1614.
26. Sukkarak, R., Likitlersuang, S., Jongpradist, P., & Jamsawang, P. (2021), "Strength and stiffness parameters for hardening soil model of rockfill materials", *Soils and Foundations*, 61:1597-1614.
27. Kasper, T., & Meschke, G. (2006), "A numerical study of the effect of soil and grout material properties and cover depth in shield tunnelling", *Computers and Geotechnics*, 33:234-247.
28. Vu, M. N., Broere, W., & Bosch, J. (2015), "Effects of cover depth on ground movements induced by shallow tunnelling", *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 50:499-506.
29. Kasper, T., & Meschke, G. (2006), "On the influence of face pressure, grouting pressure and TBM design in soft ground tunnelling", *Tunnelling and underground space technology*, 21:160-171.
30. Zhang, Q., Zhang, X. P., Wang, H. J., Liu, Q. S., Xu, D., & Tang, S. H. (2022), "Numerical study of the effect of grout material properties on ground deformation during shallow TBM tunneling", *KSCE Journal of Civil Engineering*, 26:3590-3599.
31. V. B. Maji and A. Adugna, (2016), "International Journal Of Mining And Geo-Engineering Numerical Modelling Of Tunnelling Induced Ground Deformation And Its Control," *Ijmge*, 50:183-188.
32. S. Mishra Mishra, S., Rao, K. S., Gupta, N. K., & Kumar, A. (2017), "Damage to shallow tunnels under static and dynamic loading", *Procedia engineering*, 173:1322-1329.
33. Fang, Y. S., Wu, C. T., Chen, S. F., & Liu, C. (2014), "An estimation of subsurface settlement due to shield tunneling", *Tunnelling and underground space technology*, 44:121-129.
34. Kasper, T., & Meschke, G. (2006), "A numerical study of the effect of soil and grout material properties and cover depth in shield tunnelling", *Computers and Geotechnics*, 33:234-247.
35. Vu, M. N., Broere, W., & Bosch, J. (2016), "Volume loss in shallow tunnelling", *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 59:77-90.
36. Kim1b, K., Oh2a, J., Lee3b, H., Kim3b, D., & Choi, H. (2018). Critical face pressure and backfill pressure in shield TBM tunneling on soft ground.

37. ElMouchi, A. M., Hassan, A. M., & Amer, M. I. (2018) “Performance of an existing raft foundation rested on granular soils due to TBM tunneling process”, *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 11: 1-11.
38. Tahmasebi, M. A., Shirinabadi, R., Rahimi, E., Moosavi, E., & Bangian Tabrizi, A. H. (2022), “Three-dimensional probabilistic analysis of the surface settlement based on spatial variability of soil properties: case study Zarbalizadeh NATM Tunnel”, *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 40:4895-4910.
39. Hosseini, M., Golshani, A., & Majidian, S. (2014), “Numerical modeling for construction of large span bifurcations of Niayesh tunnel, Iran”, *Electrical journal of geotechnical engineering*, 19:1457-1470.
40. Sohaei, H., Hajihassani, M., Marto, A., & Shahrababaki, M. K. (2011), “Influence of Construction Stages on Surface Settlement in NATM Tunnelling”, In *EACEF-International Conference of Civil Engineering*, 1: 024-024.